

SURVEILLANCE CARD_Lyme borreliosis_Pathogen detection in ticks collected from wild rodents in high-risk regions

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in ticks collected from wild rodents in high-risk regions testing for <i>Borrelia burgdorferi s.l.</i> (1)
2	Surveillance aim	Detection of a change of the geographic distribution. (2)
3	Target species and group	Hard ticks – Genus <i>Ixodes</i> , species <i>I. ricinus</i> and <i>I. persulcatus</i> .
4	Target sector / production type	Not applicable.
5	Geographical area covered	high-risk regions, i.e. preferred habitats of hard ticks: shady and humid woodlands, clearings with grass, open fields and bushes, urban and rural areas (3); areas with known disease presence and adjacent areas.
6	Age group	All tick stages: larvae, nymphs and adults. (4)
7	Sampling point and strategy	Live or killing - traps for wild rodents designed and placed to specifically catch a representative sample of the rodent population. Expertise in species specific trapping is required to develop a good sampling strategy covering all host species for <i>Ixodes spp.</i> .
8	Sampling time period	Ticks, are seasonally active and more likely to be detected from March to November, considering the period of maximum incidence of the disease in humans. However, the active period tick vector varies depending on the latitude, altitude and the actual temperature. (3)
9	Sampling matrix	Whole ticks.
10	Type of disease indicators	Presence of the pathogen (identification of <i>Borrelia</i> spirochetes) or DNA.
11	Sampling unit	Rodent host. Ticks on the same rodent are confounded.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Not applicable.

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Tick species identification with subsequent detection of the pathogen by polymerase chain reaction (PCR, qPCR (1)), dark-field immunofluorescence microscopy, or bacterial culture.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	<p>The component can contribute to identification of introduction of <i>Borrelia</i> in new areas, with high expected sensitivity [VectorNet, 2022]. However, results cannot be used directly for estimation of detection sensitivity or confidence of freedom since this is a biased (non-representative) sample of an unknown population.</p> <p>The probability of Borreliosis transmission to humans depends on the species composition of the local rodent population; not all tick hosts are good reservoir hosts for <i>Borrelia</i>. It is debated if better knowledge or systematic surveillance can inform ecosystem management to reduce transmission probability. (5)</p>
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Tick-borne encephalitis virus, <i>Anaplasma phagocytophilum</i> causing human granulocytic ehrlichiosis, <i>Francisella tularensis</i> causing Tularaemia, <i>Rickettsia helvetica</i> and <i>Rickettsia monacensis</i> , <i>Babesia divergens</i> and <i>Babesia microti</i> responsible for Babesiosis, Louping ill virus. (6)
18	References	<p>1) Gandy, S., Kilbride, E., Biek, R. et al. Experimental evidence for opposing effects of high deer density on tick-borne pathogen prevalence and hazard. <i>Parasites Vectors</i> 14, 509 (2021). https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-05000-0</p> <p>2) Estrada-Peña, A.; Cevdanes, A.; Sprong, H.; Millán, J. Pitfalls in Tick and Tick-Borne Pathogens Research, Some Recommendations and a Call for Data Sharing. <i>Pathogens</i> 2021, 10, 712. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10060712</p> <p>3) TECHNICAL REPORT Field sampling methods for mosquitoes, sandflies, biting midges and ticks VectorNet project 2014–2018</p>

		<p>4) Krawczyk AI, van Duijvendijk GLA, Swart A, Heylen D, Jaarsma RI, Jacobs FHH, Fonville M, Sprong H, Takken W. Effect of rodent density on tick and tick-borne pathogen populations: consequences for infectious disease risk. <i>Parasit Vectors</i>. 2020 Jan 20;13(1):34. doi: 10.1186/s13071-020-3902-0. PMID: 31959217; PMCID: PMC6971888.</p> <p>5) Steinbrink, A., Brugger, K., Margos, G. et al. The evolving story of <i>Borrelia burgdorferi sensu lato</i> transmission in Europe. <i>Parasitol Res</i> 121, 781–803 (2022). https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-022-07445-3</p> <p>6) ECDC <i>Ixodes ricinus</i> - Factsheet for experts, last updated 31 Jul 2014</p>
19	Additional comments	<p>Adult ticks can be samples when found but rodents are not often infested with adult ticks. Mice are usually infested with larvae and nymphs. While larvae are not infected with the bacteria, the testing of larvae collected on mice might be used as xenodiagnosis (i.e., testing the engorged tick for the pathogen it may have ingested during feeding on the mice). The finding of positive nymphs can indicate their infection during the larval stage or infection acquired from the mouse on which it is feeding.</p> <p>Information available about prevalence: 5 – 20 % [VectorNet, 2022]</p>